

The complexity of class polyL

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Abstract. We define the class polyL as the set of languages that can be decided in deterministic polylogarithmic space. We prove every language in NP is in polyL. In this way, we show every language in P is in polyL. Moreover, since every language in polyL is in QP, then every problem in NP can be decided in a quasi-polynomial time.

Keywords: Complexity classes · Completeness · Polynomial time · Circuit · Boolean formula.

1 Introduction

The P versus NP problem is a major unsolved problem in computer science [1]. This is considered by many to be the most important open problem in the field [1]. It is one of the seven Millennium Prize Problems selected by the Clay Mathematics Institute to carry a US\$1,000,000 prize for the first correct solution [1]. It was essentially mentioned in 1955 from a letter written by John Nash to the United States National Security Agency [1]. However, the precise statement of the $P = NP$ problem was introduced in 1971 by Stephen Cook in a seminal paper [1].

In 1936, Turing developed his theoretical computational model [10]. The deterministic and nondeterministic Turing machines have become in two of the most important definitions related to this theoretical model for computation [10]. A deterministic Turing machine has only one next action for each step defined in its program or transition function [10]. A nondeterministic Turing machine could contain more than one action defined for each step of its program, where this one is no longer a function, but a relation [10]. Another relevant advance in the last century has been the definition of a complexity class. A language over an alphabet is any set of strings made up of symbols from that alphabet [4]. A complexity class is a set of problems, which are represented as a language, grouped by measures such as the running time, memory, etc [4].

The set of languages decided by deterministic Turing machines within time f is an important complexity class denoted $TIME(f(n))$ [10]. In addition, the complexity class $NTIME(f(n))$ consists in those languages that can be decided within time f by nondeterministic Turing machines [10]. The most important complexity classes are P and NP . The class P is the union of all languages in $TIME(n^k)$ for every possible positive fixed constant k [10]. At the same time, NP consists in all languages in $NTIME(n^k)$ for every possible positive fixed

constant k [10]. NP is also the complexity class of languages whose solutions may be verified in polynomial time [10]. The biggest open question in theoretical computer science concerns the relationship between these classes: Is P equal to NP ?

A logarithmic Turing machine has a read-only input tape, a write-only output tape, and a read/write work tape [10]. The work tape may contain $O(\log n)$ symbols [10]. In computational complexity theory, $LOGSPACE$ is the complexity class containing those decision problems that can be decided by a logarithmic Turing machine which is deterministic [10]. $NLOGSPACE$ is the complexity class containing the decision problems that can be decided by a logarithmic Turing machine which is nondeterministic [10].

In computational complexity theory, $polyL$ is the complexity class of decision problems that can be solved on a deterministic Turing machine by an algorithm whose space complexity is bounded by a polylogarithmic function in the size of the input. To attack the $P = NP$ question the concept of NP -completeness is very useful [1]. We prove there is a complete problem for NP which is in $polyL$. In this way, we solve some problems which remained open until now.

2 Motivation

If any single NP -complete problem can be decided in polynomial time, then every NP problem has a polynomial time algorithm [4]. No polynomial time algorithm has yet been discovered for any NP -complete problem [5]. The biggest open question in theoretical computer science concerns the relationship between these classes: Is P equal to NP ? In 2012, a poll of 151 researchers showed that 126 (83%) believed the answer to be no, 12 (9%) believed the answer is yes, 5 (3%) believed the question may be independent of the currently accepted axioms and therefore impossible to prove or disprove, 8 (5%) said either do not know or do not care or don't want the answer to be yes nor the problem to be resolved [7]. It is fully expected that $P \neq NP$ [10]. Indeed, if $P = NP$ then there are stunning practical consequences [10]. For that reason, $P = NP$ is considered as a very unlikely event [10]. Certainly, P versus NP is one of the greatest open problems in science and thus, any breakthrough step forward for this incognita will have a great impact not only for computer science, but for many other fields as well [5].

3 Theory

Let Σ be a finite alphabet with at least two elements, and let Σ^* be the set of finite strings over Σ [3]. A Turing machine M has an associated input alphabet Σ [3]. For each string w in Σ^* there is a computation associated with M on input w [3]. We say that M accepts w if this computation terminates in the accepting state, that is $M(w) = \text{"yes"}$ [3]. Note that M fails to accept w either if this computation ends in the rejecting state, that is $M(w) = \text{"no"}$, or if the computation fails to terminate [3].

The language accepted by a Turing machine M , denoted $L(M)$, has an associated alphabet Σ and is defined by:

$$L(M) = \{w \in \Sigma^* : M(w) = \text{“yes”}\}.$$

We denote by $t_M(w)$ the number of steps in the computation of M on input w [3]. For $n \in \mathbb{N}$ we denote by $T_M(n)$ the worst case run time of M ; that is:

$$T_M(n) = \max\{t_M(w) : w \in \Sigma^n\}$$

where Σ^n is the set of all strings over Σ of length n [3]. We say that M runs in polynomial time if there is a constant k such that for all n , $T_M(n) \leq n^k + k$ [3]. In other words, this means the language $L(M)$ can be accepted by the Turing machine M in polynomial time. Therefore, P is the complexity class of languages that can be accepted in polynomial time by deterministic Turing machines [4]. A verifier for a language L is a deterministic Turing machine M , where:

$$L = \{w : M(w, c) = \text{“yes” for some string } c\}.$$

We measure the time of a verifier only in terms of the length of w , so a polynomial time verifier runs in polynomial time in the length of w [3]. A verifier uses additional information, represented by the symbol c , to verify that a string w is a member of L . This information is called certificate. NP is also the complexity class of languages defined by polynomial time verifiers [10].

A function $f : \Sigma^* \rightarrow \Sigma^*$ is a polynomial time computable function if some deterministic Turing machine M , on every input w , halts in polynomial time with just $f(w)$ on its tape [12]. Let $\{0, 1\}^*$ be the infinite set of binary strings, we say that a language $L_1 \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$ is polynomial time reducible to a language $L_2 \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$, written $L_1 \leq_p L_2$, if there is a polynomial time computable function $f : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \{0, 1\}^*$ such that for all $x \in \{0, 1\}^*$:

$$x \in L_1 \text{ if and only if } f(x) \in L_2.$$

An important complexity class is NP -complete [6]. A language $L \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$ is NP -complete if

- $L \in NP$, and
- $L' \leq_p L$ for every $L' \in NP$.

If L is a language such that $L' \leq_p L$ for some $L' \in NP$ -complete, then L is NP -hard [4]. Moreover, if $L \in NP$, then $L \in NP$ -complete [4]. A principal NP -complete problem is SAT [6]. An instance of SAT is a Boolean formula ϕ which is composed of

1. Boolean variables: x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n ;
2. Boolean connectives: Any Boolean function with one or two inputs and one output, such as \wedge (AND), \vee (OR), \neg (NOT), \Rightarrow (implication), \Leftrightarrow (if and only if);

3. and parentheses.

A truth assignment for a Boolean formula ϕ is a set of values for the variables in ϕ . A satisfying truth assignment is a truth assignment that causes ϕ to be evaluated as true. A formula with a satisfying truth assignment is a satisfiable formula. The problem *SAT* asks whether a given Boolean formula is satisfiable [6]. We define a *CNF* Boolean formula using the following terms. A literal in a Boolean formula is an occurrence of a variable or its negation [4]. A Boolean formula is in conjunctive normal form, or *CNF*, if it is expressed as an AND of clauses, each of which is the OR of one or more literals [4]. A Boolean formula is in 3-conjunctive normal form or *3CNF*, if each clause has exactly three distinct literals [4].

For example, the Boolean formula:

$$(x_1 \vee \neg x_1 \vee \neg x_2) \wedge (x_3 \vee x_2 \vee x_4) \wedge (\neg x_1 \vee \neg x_3 \vee \neg x_4)$$

is in *3CNF*. The first of its three clauses is $(x_1 \vee \neg x_1 \vee \neg x_2)$, which contains the three literals x_1 , $\neg x_1$, and $\neg x_2$. Another relevant *NP-complete* language is *3CNF* satisfiability, or *3SAT* [4]. In *3SAT*, it is asked whether a given Boolean formula ϕ in *3CNF* is satisfiable. Many problems have been proved that belong to *NP-complete* by a polynomial time reduction from *3SAT* [6]. For example, the problem *NAE 3SAT* defined as follows: Given a Boolean formula ϕ in *3CNF*, is there a truth assignment such that each clause in ϕ has at least one true literal and at least one false literal?

Another *NP-complete* problem is *CIRCUIT-SAT* [6]. A Boolean circuit is an acyclic graph $C = (V, E)$, where the nodes $V = \{1, \dots, n\}$ are called the gates of C . We can assume that all edges are of the form (i, j) where $i < j$. All nodes in the graph have in-degree (number of incoming edges) equal to 0, 1 and 2. Also, each gate $i \in V$ has a sort $c(i)$ associated with it, where $c(i) \in \{true, false, \wedge, \vee, \neg\} \cup \{x_1, x_2, \dots\}$. If $c(i) \in \{true, false\} \cup \{x_1, x_2, \dots\}$, then the in-degree of i is 0, that is, i must have no incoming edges. Gates with no incoming edges are called the inputs of C . If $c(i) = \neg$, then i has in-degree one. If $c(i) \in \{\wedge, \vee\}$, then the in-degree of i must be two. Finally, node n (the largest numbered gate in the circuit, which necessarily has no outgoing edges), is called the output gate of the circuit. Let $X(C)$ be the set of all Boolean variables that appear in the circuit C (that is, $X(C) = \{x \in X : c(i) = x \text{ for some gate } i \text{ in } C\}$). We say that a truth assignment T is appropriate for C if it is defined for all the variables in $X(C)$. The problem *CIRCUIT-SAT* asks whether a given circuit C has a truth assignment T , appropriate to C , such that $C(T) = true$. Consider, however, the same problem for circuits with no variable gates. This problem, known as *CIRCUIT-VALUE*, obviously has a polynomial time algorithm [10].

A logarithmic space Turing machine has a read-only input tape, a write-only output tape, and a read/write work tape [12]. The work tape may contain $O(\log n)$ symbols [12]. In computational complexity theory, *LOGSPACE* is the complexity class containing those decision problems that can be decided by a logarithmic space Turing machine which is deterministic [10]. *NLOGSPACE* is the complexity class containing the decision problems that can be decided by

a logarithmic space Turing machine which is nondeterministic [10]. A Boolean formula is in 2-conjunctive normal form, or $2CNF$, if it is in CNF and each clause has exactly two distinct literals. There is a problem called $2SAT$, where we asked whether a given Boolean formula ϕ in $2CNF$ is satisfiable. $2SAT$ is complete for $NLOGSPACE$ [10]. Another special case is the class of problems where each clause contains XOR (i.e. exclusive or) rather than (plain) OR operators. This is in P , since an $XOR SAT$ formula can also be viewed as a system of linear equations mod 2, and can be solved in cubic time by Gaussian elimination [9]. We denote the XOR function as \oplus . The $XOR 2SAT$ problem will be equivalent to $XOR SAT$, but the clauses in the formula have exactly two distinct literals. $XOR 2SAT$ is in $LOGSPACE$ [2], [11].

On the other hand, a polylogarithmic Turing machine may contain $O(\log^c n)$ symbols on its work tape for a positive constant c . We define $polyL$ as the complexity class of problems that can be decided by a polylogarithmic Turing machine which is deterministic. We can give a certificate-based definition for $polyL$ [3]. The certificate-based definition of $polyL$ assumes that a polylogarithmic space Turing machine has another separated read-only tape [3]. On each step of the machine the machine's head on that tape can either stay in place or move to the right [3]. In particular, it cannot reread any bit to the left of where the head currently is [3]. For that reason this kind of special tape is called "read once" [3].

Definition 1. *A language L is in $polyL$ if there exists a deterministic polylogarithmic space Turing machine with an additional special read-once input tape polynomial $p : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ such that for every $x \in \{0, 1\}^*$,*

$$x \in L \Leftrightarrow \exists u \in \{0, 1\}^{p(|x|)} \text{ such that } M \text{ accepts } \langle x, u \rangle$$

where by $M(x, u)$ we denote the computation of M where x is placed on its input tape and u is placed on its special read-once tape, and M uses at most $O(\log^c |x|)$ space on its read/write tape for every input x and a single fixed positive constant c .

4 Theoretical Framework

Theorem 1. *For a positive integer n , every set of K numbers from 1 to n can be decided by a circuit which has a size that is bounded by $\log^2 n$.*

Proof. NC^1 is the class of decision problems solvable by a uniform family of Boolean circuits, with polynomial size, depth $O(\log n)$, and fan-in 2 [8]. One of the most important known result on which is based this paper is if we have a regular language, then this will be computable by a linear size NC^1 circuit [8]. If we say that a Boolean circuit has a polynomial size $p(n)$, then n is the number of input gates. Consequently, a linear size circuit is bounded by the length $O(n)$ where n is the number of input gates. In this way, if a set of positive integers where each one has at most $\lceil \log n \rceil$ bit-length, then the size of the circuit C

which computes this subset could be bounded by $O(\log n)$ [8]. The reason is because a finite set is a regular language [10].

For a positive integer n , every set of K numbers will be a regular language, because it is finite when $1 \leq K \leq n$ [8]. Since it is a regular language, then it will be computable by a linear size NC^1 circuit [8]. Since the number of input gates should be at most $\lceil \log n \rceil$, then the size of the circuit C which computes this subset could be bounded by $O(\log n)$. However, the positive constant d in $O(\log n)$ can vary for every set of K numbers when $1 \leq K \leq n$. Nevertheless, the value of the constant d should be lesser than $\log n$ since in the opposite case the circuit will not be of linear size but quadratic size or more. For every positive constant $d < \log n$ in $O(\log n)$, the number $d \times \log n$ can always be bounded by $\log^2 n$.

5 Result

Definition 2. MAXIMUM EXCLUSIVE-OR 2-SATISFIABILITY

INSTANCE: A positive integer K and a formula ϕ that is an instance of XOR 2SAT.

QUESTION: Is there a truth assignment in ϕ such that at least K clauses are satisfiable?

We denote this problem as $MAX \oplus 2SAT$.

Theorem 2. $MAX \oplus 2SAT \in polyL$.

Proof. Given a Boolean formula ϕ that is an instance of XOR 2SAT with n variables and m clauses, we enumerate from left to right the clauses in ϕ such that the leftmost clause has the index 1 and the rightmost the number m . Therefore, a combination of K clauses in ϕ corresponds to a subset of size K from the set $\{1, 2, 3, \dots, m-1, m\}$. Due to Theorem 1, the size of the circuit C which computes this subset could be bounded by $\log^2 m$.

There will be a deterministic polylogarithmic space Turing machine which receives the circuit C in the special read-once input tape and in the input tape the given Boolean formula ϕ that is an instance of XOR 2SAT. Next, we copy the circuit C to the read/write work tape just reading each bit in the special read-once input tape from left to right until we find the blank symbol. We can copy it to the read/write work tape, because the size of C is bounded by $\log^2 m$. After that, we evaluate in ascending order the numbers in the set $\{1, 2, 3, \dots, m-1, m\}$ just to verify if there are at least K numbers which leads to an acceptance. This can be done each time in $O(\log^2 m)$, because CIRCUI T VALUE can be decided in linear time [10]. Consequently, this can be decided in $O(\log^2 m)$ space on the read/write work tape. Besides, we can count the number of different acceptances with a positive integer d that will have at most $\lceil \log m \rceil$ bit-length. Furthermore, if we obtain in the counting that $d > m$ or $d < K$, then we reject. In this way, this process remains in $O(\log^2 m)$ space.

Finally, if there are at least K acceptances between the numbers 1 and m , then we compute in the read/write work tape the Boolean formula $\psi = c_{i_1} \wedge$

$c_{i_2} \dots \wedge c_{i_K} \dots$ such that each number i_j is accepted by C . Since $XOR\ 2SAT$ is in $LOGSPACE$ [2], [11], then we can decide ψ in logarithmic space. Notice that, we do not need to copy ψ to the read/write work tape since the membership in ψ of any clause c_{i_j} in the input tape can be done in polylogarithmic space by an evaluation in C . In this way, we finally accept in case of ψ is satisfiable otherwise we reject the chosen input and certificate. All this process can be done in a deterministic polylogarithmic space just reading at once the additional special tape. Moreover, the size of the certificate is polynomial due to the size and the depth of C is polylogarithmic. In conclusion, we show $MAX \oplus 2SAT$ complies with the certificate-based definition of $polyL$ and thus, $MAX \oplus 2SAT \in polyL$ [3].

Theorem 3. $MAX \oplus 2SAT \in NP$ -complete.

Proof. It is trivial to see $MAX \oplus 2SAT \in NP$ [10]. Given a Boolean formula ϕ in $3CNF$ with n variables and m clauses, we create the following formulas for each clause $c_i = (x \vee y \vee z)$ in ϕ , where x , y and z are literals,

$$P_i = (x \oplus y) \wedge (y \oplus z) \wedge (x \oplus z).$$

We can see P_i has exactly two satisfiable clauses if and only if at least one member of $\{x, y, z\}$ is true and at least one member of $\{x, y, z\}$ is false. Hence, we can create the Boolean formula ψ as the conjunction of the P_i formulas for every clause c_i in ϕ , such that $\psi = P_1 \wedge \dots \wedge P_m$. Finally, we obtain that

$$\phi \in NAE\ 3SAT \text{ if and only if } (\psi, 2 \times m) \in MAX \oplus 2SAT.$$

Consequently, we prove $NAE\ 3SAT \leq_p MAX \oplus 2SAT$ where $NAE\ 3SAT \in NP$ -complete. To sum up, we show $MAX \oplus 2SAT \in NP$ -hard and $MAX \oplus 2SAT \in NP$ and thus, $MAX \oplus 2SAT \in NP$ -complete.

Theorem 4. $NP \subseteq polyL$.

Proof. If any single NP -complete problem belongs to $polyL$, then every NP problem is in $polyL$ [4]. Hence, as a consequence of Theorems 2 and 3, then $NP \subseteq polyL$.

Lemma 1. $NP \subseteq QP$.

Proof. Quasi-polynomial time algorithms are algorithms that run slower than polynomial time, yet not so slow as to be exponential time. The worst case running time of a quasi-polynomial time algorithm is $2^{O((\log n)^c)}$ for some fixed $c > 0$. QP is the class of languages decided by quasi-polynomial time algorithms. Just as $LOGSPACE \subseteq P$, $polyL \subseteq QP$. Since $NP \subseteq polyL$, then $NP \subseteq QP$.

Lemma 2. $P \not\subseteq polyL$.

Proof. The only proven relationship between $polyL$ and P is that $polyL \neq P$. Since $NP \subseteq polyL$ and $P \subseteq NP$, then $P \not\subseteq polyL$.

6 Conclusion

No one has been able to find a polynomial time algorithm for any of more than 300 important known *NP-complete* problems [6]. Most complexity theorists already assume P is not equal to NP , but no one has found an accepted and valid proof yet [7]. There are several consequences if P is not equal to NP , such as many common problems cannot be solved efficiently [1]. However, a proof of $P = NP$ will have stunning practical consequences, because it leads to efficient methods for solving some of the important problems in NP [1]. The consequences, both positive and negative, arise since various *NP-complete* problems are fundamental in many fields [1]. In this work, we make a breakthrough step forward to a solution to this problem proving the new results $P \not\subseteq polyL$ and $NP \subseteq QP$.

References

1. Aaronson, S.: $P \stackrel{?}{=} NP$. Electronic Colloquium on Computational Complexity, Report No. 4 (2017)
2. Alvarez, C., Greenlaw, R.: A compendium of problems complete for symmetric logarithmic space. *Computational Complexity* **9**(2), 123–145 (2000)
3. Arora, S., Barak, B.: *Computational complexity: a modern approach*. Cambridge University Press (2009)
4. Cormen, T.H., Leiserson, C.E., Rivest, R.L., Stein, C.: *Introduction to Algorithms*. The MIT Press, 3rd edn. (2009)
5. Fortnow, L.: The status of the P versus NP problem. *Communications of the ACM* **52**(9), 78–86 (2009)
6. Garey, M.R., Johnson, D.S.: *Computers and Intractability: A Guide to the Theory of NP-Completeness*. San Francisco: W. H. Freeman and Company, 1 edn. (1979)
7. Gasarch, W.I.: Guest column: The second $P \stackrel{?}{=} NP$ poll. *ACM SIGACT News* **43**(2), 53–77 (2012)
8. Koucky, M.: Circuit complexity of regular languages (April 2012), at <http://www.cse.iitm.ac.in/~jayalal/teaching/CS6840/2012/project/Regular-Sunil-slides.pdf>
9. Moore, C., Mertens, S.: *The Nature of Computation*. Oxford University Press (2011)
10. Papadimitriou, C.H.: *Computational complexity*. Addison-Wesley (1994)
11. Reingold, O.: Undirected connectivity in log-space. *Journal of the ACM* **55**(4), 1–24 (2008)
12. Sipser, M.: *Introduction to the Theory of Computation*, vol. 2. Thomson Course Technology Boston (2006)